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Community Policing: Initiatives and Challenges

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Abstract:

Community policing is a relatively new addition to law enforcement which aims to increase the interaction between local police and the people and neighborhoods they serve. The immediate aim of community policing is to mitigate and prevent crime which in turn enhances the faith of community in police. The initiative of community policing is silent revolution towards rising internal insecurities which is considered as one of the biggest threat of present times. This study attempts to understand the concept of community policing and throws light on various initiatives and challenges faced by community policing programs. Further it provides suggestions to overcome the challenges to make community policing a success.

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Introduction:

Law enforcement agencies in India are facing serious challenges today. Criminalization of politics, growing nexus between power structure and criminals and inefficient state machinery has made the tasks of maintaining public order and crime prevention difficult. Police agencies, all over the world, have been devising various mechanisms to face these emerging challenges. Community policing has emerged as an important one such mechanism. Community policing can be understood as an alliance between the police and the community that identifies and solves community problems. With the police no longer the sole guardians of law and order, all members of the community become active allies in the effort to enhance the safety and quality of neighborhoods. Community policing has far-reaching implications. The stretched attitude on crime control and prevention, the new emphasis on making community members active participants in the process of problem solving, and the patrol officers' pivotal role in community policing require profound changes within the police organization. The neighborhood patrol officer, backed by the police organization, helps community members mobilizes support and resources to solve problems and enhance their quality of life. Community members voice their concerns, contribute advice, and take action to address these concerns. Creating a constructive partnership will require the energy, creativity, understanding, and patience of all involved.

Concept of Community Policing:

Community policing is a philosophical approach to policing; it is not a program or set of programs or tactics. Police departments that embrace the community policing philosophy work in partnership with the community to address local public safety problems and make organizational changes to support these efforts.¹ Community policing involves "reforming Community Policing decision-making processes and creating new cultures within police departments: it is not a packet of specific tactical plans, it assumes a commitment to broadly focused, problem-oriented policing and requires that police be responsive to citizens' demands when they decide what local problems are and set their priorities" (Rohe)². The community policing involves three components such as community partnership, problem solving and organizational transformation³ which plays pivotal role in its application.

Community partnership symbolizes adopting a policing perspective that surpasses the standard law enforcement emphasis. This enlarged outlook recognizes the value of activities that contribute to the orderliness and well-being of a neighborhood. These activities could include: helping accident or crime victims, providing emergency medical services, helping resolve domestic and neighborhood conflicts (e.g., family violence, landlord-tenant disputes, or racial harassment), working with residents and local businesses to improve neighborhood conditions, controlling automobile and pedestrian traffic, providing emergency social services and referrals to those at risk), protecting the exercise of constitutional rights (e.g., guaranteeing a person's right to speak, protecting lawful assemblies from disruption), and providing a model of citizenship (helpfulness, respect for others, honesty, and fairness). Building trust needs persistent efforts and effective public relation campaigns. But trust must be achieved before police can assess the needs of the community and construct the close ties that will engender community support. On the other hand, problem solving is a broad term that implies more than simply the elimination and prevention of crimes. Problem solving is based on the assumption that "crime and disorder can be reduced in small geographic areas by carefully studying the characteristics of problems in the area, and then applying the appropriate resources" and on the assumption that "Individuals make choices based on the opportunities presented by the immediate physical and social characteristics of an area, by manipulating these factors, people will be less inclined to act in an offensive manner." The changes that a community policing agency must make in its management, organizational structure, personnel practices, and technology and information systems in support of community policing are referred to as organizational transformation. The community policing philosophy focuses on the way that departments are organized and managed and how the infrastructure can be changed to support the philosophical shift behind community policing. It encourages the application of modern management practices to increase efficiency and effectiveness. Community policing emphasizes changes in organizational structures to institutionalize its adoption and infuse it throughout the entire department, including the way it is managed and organized, its personnel, and its technology.

The Advocates for community policing have highlighted many reasons why community policing is beneficial to society. These arguments were broken down into three areas by Segrave and Ratcliffe⁴ i.e. community specific advantages, police specific benefits and shared benefits.

The community specific advantages, as pointed out by Segrave and Ratcliffe include mobilisation and empowerment of communities to identify and respond to concerns; improved local physical and social environment; increase in positive attitudes towards police; and reduced fear of crime. Further Police-specific benefits are improved police–community relationship; improved community perception of police ‘legitimacy’; and an increase in officer satisfaction with their work. The authors mention the following as shared benefits of the community policing: a decreased potential for police–citizen conflict; a reduction in crime rates; a better flow of information between the police and community; and better implementation of crime prevention and crime control activities, as a result of both parties working towards shared goals.

Community Policing initiatives in various countries:

The Community Policing is being adopted all around the world. Some of the famous community policing initiatives in the world have been discussed below:

Koban in Japan

Koban, in Japanese Language means mini station. It is a system of community policing which originated in Japan but has got acceptance around the world. In this system of community policing every Japanese Police graduate has to serve for several years at one of these Kobans. There are around 15,000 Kobans in Japan which receive half of the total number of public requests for assistance. The Police officers stationed at Kobans visits the houses of the area twice in a year. In Japan under the Koban system one officer generally remains in the Police mini station, while a partner roams the territory having a few blocks to a few square miles, depending on the population on foot or on the standard white frame Police bicycle. The Koban also provides local lost and found service to the community.⁵

Principles of Koban:

Basic principle of Koban is the safety of the whole nation, based upon the public peace and safety of respective communities.

Functioning of Koban:⁶

- Community Police Officers (CPO) are in charge of initial response regarding a variety of violations until plain clothes police officers from a police station take over the case.
- CPOs make regular patrols of their jurisdictions mainly on foot, visiting residents and business enterprises regarding emergency contact and hearing request.
- Attend various problems and nuisances including domestic disputes, unreasonable noise and disruptive gatherings of juveniles in their jurisdiction.
- Shift system according to the needs of each region.
- Basic duties of officers includes standing watch in front of the police box, sitting watch from inside, and field duties consisting of patrols and door to door visits to homes and business.

Success of Koban:

Koban is very successful as this in Japan originated system has got acceptance around the world. Many countries like Singapore and Columbia followed Koban system in their respective countries.

Neighborhood Police Post (NPP) in Singapore⁷

The Neighbourhood Police Post (NPP) in Singapore was initiated in 1983 drawing inspiration from the Koban system. With the introduction of NPP community policing became the established mode of policing in Singapore. The success of community policing in Singapore is reflected in terms of the arrests made with the help of public, together with the active participation of the people in the Neighbourhood Watch Scheme. The efforts made by NPP officers resulted in making the public aware about the crimes in the neighbourhood and adopting preventive measures as suggested by the NPP officers. The Police in Singapore has been able to keep crime under control signifying the success of this community policing initiative.

Features of NPP:

- Community based crime prevention- Where the community were advised on crime and encouraged to crime prevention measures by police.

- Re-orientation of patrol - To emphasis proactive provision of sources where police patrol forces not only respond to calls for assistance but also gather more information to solve the problems in the larger term.
- Decentralization of command - Where the police officers at the lowest level of the hierarchy are given authority to solve local crime, public order and public safety problems.
- People's participation – By putting a degree of accountability to local communities where police officers devote sufficient effort to address issues and problems and concern the local community most.

Operation Cul-de-Sac (OCDS) of Los Angeles Police Department (LAPD)⁸

The Operation Cul-de-Sac (OCDS) began in 1990 under the sponsorship of the Los Angeles Police Department (LAPD). It was an attempt to examine the potential for community oriented policing in high crime areas and to determine the best initiatives designed to build police citizen partnerships. OCDS was one of the first programs in the country to use street closures for crime control, and the idea developed after the accidental discovery of the effectiveness of installing sawhorses in reducing drug activity in a well-known LA drug district.

Working of OCDS:

Under this programme, LAPD, with the agreement of the residents involved, placed iron gates on streets marking the outer boundaries of the OCDS area. Foot, bicycle, and horse patrols were introduced for a short time in order to increase inter personal contacts between the police and citizens. Six officers were permanently assigned to the area, where they joined forces with community groups to clean up graffiti and develop neighbourhood watch programme while maximizing positive contacts with residents. During the 1st year, the LAPD also implemented other community police projects, such as the assignment of 15 officers who were tasked with getting to know the residents and neighborhood; the development of task forces to remove signs of physical disorder (e.g., remove garbage or graffiti); and the creation of block clubs.

Community Oriented Policing Services (COPS) in USA⁹

The Community Oriented Policing Services (COPS) programme was launched in the year 1994 with an aim to advance community policing in all jurisdictions across the United States of America. Under this programme, the grants are awarded to state, local and tribal law enforcement agencies throughout the USA so that they can hire and train law enforcement officers to participate in community policing, purchase and deploy new crime fighting technologies, develop and test new and innovative policing strategies. COPS grants are managed by the COPS office, which was created in 1994 by Department of Justice to oversee the COPS programme. Grant funds under this program could have been used to:

- hire new police officers;
- rehire police officers who have been laid off; and
- obtain equipment or support systems and provide overtime pay, if it results in an increase of the number of officers deployed in community-oriented policing.

Neighborhood Oriented Policing (NOP) in Joliet, Illinois

Neighbourhood Oriented Policing (NOP) in Joliet began in 1992 with the setting up of specialised units consisting of volunteers assigned full time to the NOP. Under this programme, these volunteers went door to door introducing themselves, providing residents with cellular phone numbers where they could be reached while on duty. Officers attended neighbourhood watch meetings and promoted after school opportunities for young people. They spent time with school children during recess and on their lunch hours and served as guest readers for younger children.¹⁰

Activities of NOP:¹¹

The NOP Unit's special focus is to proactively engage the residents of that neighborhood community with the objective of identifying neighborhood crime and disorder problems. Other activities include:

- Entering into trespass agreements with property owners;
- Identifying drug related and prostitution areas for targeted enforcement;
- Utilizing crime prevention through environmental design principals;
- Assisting cooperative landlords with evictions and providing training to landlords;

- Abating problem locations utilizing the city's Nuisance Abatement Program;
- Analyze crime statistics and organize special details to address the increase in criminal activity;
- Participate in community group/ Neighborhood Watch meetings and provide feedback during meetings.

The Mercaz Shitur Kahiliti (MaShaK: Community Policing in Israel)

The Mercaz Shitur Kahiliti (MaShaK) meaning Community Policing Mini Station was an important innovation of community policing in Israel. It was established in Israel in 1995 with a purpose to meet needs of the citizens and to integrate the resources and goals of the Police with those of Local Government Authorities and community agencies and Community Policing Centre. The concept was strongly supported by commanders in the stations, and there was a general feeling among commanders that the MaShaK was an effective tool in reducing crime, and strengthening contacts with the community.

Objectives of MaShak:¹²

The main objective of MaShak is to bring closed relationship between police and the public. Other objectives are as follows:

- remaking of the Israeli police officer in terms of philosophy and behavior;
- restructuring of police work;
- restructuring of management within the police;
- change in the relationship between the police and local authorities;
- change in the relationship between the police and the public; and
- change in the priorities of police work.

Working of MaShak:

The Community Policing Centres were set up in outlying locations such as rural areas, areas with large concentrations of immigrants or ultra orthodox, Arab communities and others. In some places there are mobile community patrolman on motor cycles who provide police services on public beaches and at commercial and tourist sites. The Community Policing Centres provides

services such as receiving complaints and reports from citizens, dealing with daily nuisances, environmental infractions, assorted disputes and others. In addition, Community Policing Unit in Israel also undertakes activities in collaboration with Civil Guard volunteers and neighbourhood residents. Together they run special projects in the area of crime prevention for immigrants and senior citizens and preventive programmes such as The Safe School which caters on the activities to prevent juvenile delinquency.¹³

Community Policing Initiatives in India:

Not much is known about when the system of Community policing was started in India but it is believed that this system started during the Mauryan Empire. In Kautaliya's *Arthashastra* it is found that there was a system of village policing to protect the village from any crime and the power of this system was given to the village headman. The system helped in prevention and detection of crime in the villages. During the Muslim period from the 12th Century onwards, policing of the vast rural areas was left to be done by the village headman with the help of local chowkidars.

After India got independence in 1947 many states have taken many initiatives regarding Community Policing. Some of the important initiatives taken by the states are given below:

Karnataka Village Defence Party

The Karnataka Village Defence Parties are constituted in the villages in accordance with the provisions of the Karnataka Village Defence Parties Act, 1964 (Karnataka Act. No.34 of 1964). These Village Defence Parties are voluntary bodies whose members are appointed by the Superintendent of Police of the concerned districts. The members of the Village Defence Parties shall discharge such functions and duties in relation of the defence of villages, the protection of person, the security of property and the preservation of public order in such villages as may be assigned to them in accordance with the provisions of the Act and the rules made there under. The head of every Village Defence Party is called "Dalapathi" and he is appointed by the Superintendent of Police of the district. In deserving cases Superintendents of Police may sanction rewards and issue certificate of merit to deserving members and Dalapathis of the village Defence Parties.¹⁴

Mohalla Committee Movement Trust, Mumbai¹⁵

It was set up after 1992-93 Hindu-Muslim riots that paralyzed Mumbai (Bombay) and killed around 1000 people. The Mohalla Committee was formed under the initiative of former Mumbai Commissioner, J.F. Ribiero. The Chairman of the Mohalla Committee Movement Trust was Mr. Deshmukh. After 1992 riots, people from all walks of life who were survivors, came together and along with the police worked out a simple workable idea that became a reality.

The Mohalla Committee which is also known as the Peace Committee, has now become a part of the civil society structure in the city that usually has little time or space. The concept works on the simple principle that gives people some power and makes them responsible for it. Every Mohalla Committee, and there are 24 in the city, has a sizeable number of people from the area who are regarded as elders or who have a standing of their own, or have the charisma to make others listen to them. The primary task of the committee members is to maintain more than cordial relations between the two communities, largely Hindus and Muslims.

Functions of Mohalla Committee:

The main functions of Mohalla Committee include:

- Intervene in disputes even personal or domestic quarrels if need be;
- Organize little meetings or a variety of programmes and liaison with the nearest police station in their efforts to maintain peace.
- If rumours go around they defuse them before it can cause any harm.
- Other activities focuses on the issues related to (a) complaints related to the work of the police of the area; (b) civic issues like health, availability of water, environment, and garbage disposal; (c) facilities for education for the children and youth in the area; (d) activities promoting communal harmony like celebrating festivals of different communities.

The Parivar Paramarsh Kendra, Sagar District, Madhya Pradesh

It is a unique effort in community policing where the Kendra focuses on resolving family conflicts. It is done by identifying the causes that contribute to family discord. Here the Kendra

takes up a social decision making role and strives to save a family from being broken. It mainly acts as a center for counseling family problems. The idea behind such a venture is to improve the social environment, in a city by solving family disputes. By solving personal problems at an early stage, the police personnel have found that this often prevents criminal tendencies within an individual to further violate the law. The Kendra was formed under the umbrella of the District Police, Sagar and was initiated on 10th October 1995.¹⁶

Working of The Parivar Paramarsh Kendra:¹⁷

The Family Counseling Center can be termed as embodiment of mutual trust, understanding, love, cooperation and above all a sheltering place to the forlorn young couple. Each Family Counseling Centre has 5 to 10 Women Counselors/NGO members. They attend the centres daily from 11 a.m. to 5 p.m. A total of about 70 Women counselors are rendering there valuable services in these Family Counseling Centres. The steps are as follows:

1. On receipt of a complaint, women counselors register it and discuss problems with the upset party. Thereafter summons are issued to the respondents to appear before the Family Counseling Centre on a specific date and time.
2. The Counselors try to bring a psychological change in their attitude towards each other and efforts are made to bring an amicable solution to their grievances through mutual understanding.
3. Where parties do not agree for compromise, in such cases the aggrieved women are supported and necessary help is extended by way of legal aid.
4. To avoid inconvenience due to recurrence, disputed cases are kept under surveillance and are followed up regularly. The follow up action has tremendous positive psychological effect on both the parties besides providing factual information.
5. To give incentive to the settled families, they are invited in social gatherings organised by the centre.

Success of The Parivar Paramarsh Kendra:

Counseling at these centres has produced good results. A majority of citizens want to refrain from legal actions and they are now turning towards the Family Counseling Centre to settle their

disputes amicably. Kendra has been functioning successfully over the last many years and has contributed a lot to society. By satisfying the community by involving them in performing such an important service as saving families from breaking, the police has also effectively improved their image from being authoritarian and be a more people friendly police.

The Community Policing Initiative In Assam

Prahari:

Community Policing in Assam was started on 3rd July 1996 when a meeting of the citizens under Panbazar Police Station in Guwahati to discuss the concept of neighbourhood watch scheme and promote community participation in policing. The community policing initiative was also aimed at changing the attitude of the average policeman at the police stations towards the public, to make them people friendly and to improve their living and working conditions. The goal of Prahari was to tackle social problems and bring the police and community closer.¹⁸

Nagrik Samities:

Nagrik Samities meaning citizens committee introduced in each ward in Guwahati and established community Liaison Groups (CLGs) at the field levels. Bureau of Police Research and Development supported the community policing initiative of Assam under United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) project. One of the outcomes of community policing has been the mobilization of the people against insurgency in Assam. Thus, in some areas, the people started guarding vital installations, bridges and railway tracks to prevent sabotage by extremists. Forums like the CLGs, Nagrik Samities helped to wean people away from the extremists to the state and, to that extent, reduced the base on which extremism thrives. In fact, in Guwahati, people have taken active steps to thwart extremist designs for carrying out large scale sabotage by guarding vital installations physically e.g. about 300 volunteers formed a physical ring round the Guwahati refinery for 15 days to prevent it from being blown up by the ULFA during the Independence day in August 2000. Similarly other groups have guarded railway bridges. During elections, villagers volunteer their services to see that road communications are not disrupted by extremists so that election parties can go to the remotes areas and conduct elections and com e

back safely. In one instance the local citizens group being aware of the problems of police took cudgels on its behalf against wrong reporting.¹⁹

Community Policing in Andhra Pradesh

Andhra Pradesh Police has taken many initiatives regarding Community Policing in the State. Some of the initiatives are discussed below:

Maithari:²⁰

It is an initiative which was launched in 2000, by the Andhra Pradesh Police throughout the state. The mission of Maithri was to render courteous, compassionate and caring responsive police personnel and increase public confidence in police with respect to maintenance of peace and order and build in a feeling of safety from crime. It rests on the belief that contemporary community problems require a decentralized and personalized police approach, which involves citizens who finally learn how to police themselves.

Several crimes have been prevented and detected on account of this programme in the state. Many community outreach programmes relating to eradication of superstitions, traffic awareness, women protection, street children, marital disputes, AIDS awareness, faction crime, etc., have been organised with the help of Maithri Committees.

Maithri members have played an important role in managing crowds during major festivals and maintaining communal harmony in several parts of the State. There is perceptible change in the attitude of the police towards the people and their problems and towards human rights, after launching the programme. Public perception of the police is also undergoing change for the better.

Police Mee Kosam (Police for you):²¹

This experiment of community policing is undertaken during 2001-2004 to control left wing extremism of CPI (Maoist) group. Through Police Mee Kosam, Adilabad police tried to tackle the issue on two fronts with mission of fighting against crime and not criminals. Firstly through backward area development and rehabilitation of surrender Maoist and secondly taking stern

action against law breakers. The primary plan in this whole initiative was to make the community participation in development in remote areas with police as facilitator while tackling extremism. Reforms were inducted into policing and the police tried to project its human face in while discharging their duties. In Adilabad, the police department brought about rapid reforms and took up developmental programmes in rural areas under the name Police Mee Kosam (police for you). The major reform in policing was to respect tribal customs and sentiments by the personnel through gestures like greetings like 'Ram Ram' or by removing their shoes while entering the home of the tribal's.

This experiment is the recipient of 2004 Community policing finalist award and special honor in homeland security category from International Association of Chiefs of Police (IACP), USA and ITT Industries Limited announced in IACP's annual conference at Los Angeles, USA from November 13-17, 2004.

Project Asara:²²

Through Project Aasara, law enforcement officials of the Nalgonda district in the state partnered with government and non-government sources, including the Red Cross, to tackle the crime and in rehabilitating "sex workers." Aasara means shelter or support, and that was what police with other stake holders attempted to provide to victims of trafficking. The role of the police was shifted from one of strictly law enforcement to an agency that fosters "rescue, rehabilitation and reintegration" into society.

Community Policing: Friends of Police, Tamil Nadu²³

The Friends of Police (FOP) is a holistic and pro-active concept that lends a psychological approach to policing. It is a true example of police public partnership where citizens have been empowered along with the police. It was started in 1993 in Ramnad District of Tamilnadu. The programme provides opportunities for ordinary citizens to effectively contribute to the prevention and detection of crime. Any member of the public, male or female who is not involved in civil or criminal case can become a member of FOP. The members of FOP can provide useful information leading to solving of crimes. FOP members can also prevent any abuse of police power because of easy accessibility to the station house officer and other senior personnel. This experiment has been able to create channels of information flow between the

police and the citizens. This has often been useful while locating information and solving cases. The experiment has also helped the police to come closer to the community. It has tried to impart fairness, transparency and impartiality in the working of the police and has been effective over the last five years in Tamil Nadu.

Objectives of FOP:

1. To separate the friends from the foes of the police or "the chaff from the grain".
2. To enable members of the public without regard to caste, creed or status, to establish rapport with police force. It is a method of people empowerment.
3. To promote crime awareness among the people and enable prevention of crimes.
4. To promote a sense of civic responsibilities and duties of the public a means of educating the general public. To learn as well as to teach human values.
5. To act as a force multiplier by involving the FOPs in community policing. With the existing low police-public ratio, COPs along with FOPs can deter and prevent crimes.
6. To evolve a mechanism to get feedback.
7. To channelise local resources at short notice to meet any eventuality.
8. To make available a potential pool of manpower resources with positive attitudes to the police to meet the requirement of police.
9. To increase transparency and openness in the police.
10. FOP can make steps towards policing with consent instead of the present image of policing with contempt.
11. To educate the members of the public about their role and responsibility in policing.
12. To enable police to prevent commission of criminal offences.

Community Policing Initiative in Himachal Pradesh²⁴

A Community Policing Scheme/ Samudayak Police Yojna was introduced in Himachal Pradesh in November 2000 in order to mobilize public support and involve active public participation in prevention and detection of crime and maintenance of law and order. It was initially introduced in 22 out of 83 police stations in the State. Under this scheme a police station is divided into sectors corresponding to wards of Panchayat. Bigger wards have more sectors. All the household members in a particular sector constitute the Peoples Policing Committee of that sector. Each

sector has an active group consisting of 6 respectable persons of that locality, one home guard, one chowkidar and one Police Constable / Head Constable as Secretary. One member of the Active Group is the convener. As a result of the positive feedback of the State, the scheme was introduced in all the police stations of the state.

Objectives of Samudayak Police Yojna:

Main objectives of Samudayak Police Yojna in Himachal Pradesh is to achieved the following:

- Community should be able to identify and solve their problems;
- Community should be able to prevent crime on their own;
- Community should be able to assist the police in ensuring safer living conditions; and
- Community should feel safe and be satisfied with Police Services and efforts.

Sahayata: A Community Policing Initiative in Nadia District, West-Bengal

Sahatya means assistance, is an experiment that has been conceived as a service delivery platform to resolve, through counselling, disputes within family and also between neighbours. In this experiment the police is an active agent in resolving disputes and that too through an inexpensive and prompt system. Community involvement has been kept as its prime objective. It started in 2001 in Nadia district, West Bangal. Sahayata Centres were set up at all the Police Stations. Complain. Boxes were placed outside these centers having proper glow-sign boards to enable people to drop their complaints.²⁵

Saanjh Project in Punjab²⁶

Punjab Police on the recommendations of Punjab Governance Reforms Commission has launched a community policing initiative called Saanjh Project in 2011. Under the Saanjh Community Policing programme in Punjab, a six-tier body has been constituted. The Community Affairs Division and the State Level Steering Committee are placed at the apex, which provides policy guidelines, support for capacity building and strengthens systems of planning, management, participatory and integrity mechanisms. At the District level, Community Police Resource Centres (CPRCs) and District Level Committees have been set up to ensure

networking of CPRCs with other government departments and administrative structures. It also streamlines the training of personnel at the District level and coordinates with the fifth and sixth tier i.e. Sub-Divisional Community Police Suvidha Centres (CPSCs) and Police Station Outreach Centres (PSOCs) at the Police Station level. The CPRCs, CPSCs and PSOCs are autonomous registered societies. Through Saanjh Project, the citizens are provided dignified access to Police related services and a forum to implement community oriented programmes.

Main Features of Saanjh:

The Community Police Centres (CPRC, CPSC and PSOC) are autonomous registered societies in partnership with representatives of the police, the administration and civil society. The main features of these are:

- Collectively managed by the community and the police – including Government officials from departments, such as, Health, Education, Welfare and representatives from NGOs, academics, local bodies, etc.).
- Community-police collaboration from decision-making to implementation.
- A pool of police and community resources.

These centres i.e. at the district sub-division and police station level centres are nodal places for police-community extension services.

Community Policing initiatives by Chandigarh Police

Chandigarh Police has been regularly undertaking Community Policing initiatives in Chandigarh. It has established a Cell named Community Relations Unit (CRU) for this purpose. This cell is functioning under the supervision of a DSP rank officer who reports directly to SSP city. Some of the Community Policing initiatives of Chandigarh Police are discussed below:

Neighbourhood Watch Scheme:

Chandigarh police has a functional neighbourhood watch scheme which is operational in thirteen sectors of the city. The main objective of neighbourhood watch scheme in Chandigarh is to enhance safety and security of the area by police-community interface and to improve interaction

among the citizens and the police by organizing social, cultural and sports events. The above objectives of the scheme are being met by using the following techniques:-

1. Police public meetings.
2. Door-to-door visits by beat staff.
3. Motivating citizens to install home security devices.
4. Verification of antecedents of servants and attendants.
5. Special consideration for senior citizens.
6. Organizing culture, social and sports events.
7. Generating data bank about citizens by publishing citizens' directory.
8. Regular inter-action with the Residents Welfare Associations.
9. Enhancing the physical security of the sector by closing unwanted openings and other measures.
10. Devising strategies for keeping track on the hawkers and other vendors.

Young Heroes for Safe City:

It is a programme for sensitizing the residents of the city about crime and their preventive measures by involving youth from the colleges of the city. This initiative includes do's and don'ts for senior citizens, tips for prevention from burglaries and thefts, home security tips and don'ts related to the drugs. Three colleges and one club of the city took the lead in this initiative.

In this initiative Chandigarh Police with youngsters distributed pamphlets to citizens to make them aware about their safety and security. These pamphlets include symptoms of drug addicts, home safety tips, prevention from theft, safety and security tips, safety of senior citizens and working of Community Relations Officers and Community Liaison Groups.

Work for Fun for Senior Citizens':

Walk for fun for senior citizens initiative was launched by Chandigarh Police in collaboration with Chandigarh Senior Citizens' Association. The main aim of this initiative is to reduce loneliness of senior citizens and to have interaction with Chandigarh Police for the safety and security of senior citizens. Persons participating in the event have to provide their medical certificate and their consent on participation in the event.

Sports activities:

Chandigarh police from time to time organized sports events to maintain close contact with the residents of the city, some of the events includes IGP Golf Tournament and Gully Cricket League.

1. IGP Golf Tournament:

Chandigarh police with Times of India organized two day event of Golf Tournament, starting with welcome dinner at Taj Hotel on March 3, 2012. It was an initiative of IGP, Sh. P.K. Srivastava, Chandigarh Police and the tournament saw participation of over 96 prominent golfers of the region competing in five categories.

2. Gully Cricket League:

The CPGCL initiative was conceived as an ‘Opportunity for Partnership-in-Excellence between Chandigarh Police and Amar Ujala Publications Ltd.’ It was seen as a unique proposition, which would provide opportunities to both the organizations, which included to: (i) build a unique community connect through the game of cricket; (ii) engage youth in a constructive exercise and give them a platform to prove themselves; (iii) improve and enhance the image of Chandigarh Police; and (iv) initiate a venture with the potential of becoming an example to be emulated world over by other Police agencies. The initiative was launched as ‘Amar Ujala Chandigarh Police Gully Cricket League’ and both the parties decided to share the responsibilities for conducting this League successfully.

Challenges of Community Policing:

Implementations of community policing initiatives have posed various problems to the police agencies in India. Some of these are as follows:

- i. The experiments and programmes are not always adapted to community's needs.
- ii. They work well in times of crisis. Once the emergency passes, they lose momentum.
- iii. The police interest flags after some time.
- iv. Some police often consider it a diversion from their main activities.

v. Police Community relations have mostly remain urban exercises in India to the neglect of villages.

vi. Most of the programmes gradually get politicized.

vii. Suspicion and misunderstandings always creep in after some time

viii. The programmes are sometimes weighted in favour of preventing property offences.

ix. Some individual police officers make a difference. When they go, the programme suffers.

x. The tendency to establish temporary, chiefly improvisational policies and procedures to deal with specific problems and tasks characterizes community-policing efforts in India.

Suggestions for Effective Community Policing in India:

From the above discussion it is found that community policing is one of the best style of policing in which police and community help each other to control crime and maintenance of law and order in the society but it has many problems also. Some suggestions for the effective community policing in India are given below:

- For number of reasons the collapse of public order, ineffective policing and delays in justice affect society in an extremely adverse way, such collapses and delays hampers the true spirit of community policing initiatives. There is need to improve upon such malpractices.
- Ineffective and obsolete public relation practices is another major hurdle in establishing the trust among citizens, until and unless community connect is not up to the mark, it would be impossible to achieve the desired results of community policing.
- Lack of data is proving another hindrance in making the community policing work. There is dire need of creating community policing data base has also been created with the help of the National Police Academy, Institute for Social Sciences and other state level universities.

- Lack of evaluation of community policing program is one the major flaws in plugging the research gaps of theory and practice. Such gaps need to be plugged in immediately to check the practices.
- There is need to update technology as it is real challenge for police to cope up with the changing times. These days' criminals have access to sophisticated technological tools and devices and police is lacking in very nature of tackling them.
- Abuse of power within the police is another significant reason for failure of establishing the trust among masses. People feel that there is hardly and scope of establishing mutual trust among police and public.
- Regular efforts should be made with NGOs and other wings of civil society to understand the needs and problems. Constant and periodic interaction is key to success.
- It's time to initiate the community policing practices through coordinated efforts of colleges students and various wings like NSS and NCC. Regular interaction with the welfare associations holds the key in establishing the connect and winning the trust.
- There is need to hold regular games, nuked natak and effective public services advertisements and campaigns to establish effective connect.

Conclusion: Connect with civil society has helped the police in checking crime and apprehending criminals by anticipating their criminal strategies. To make community connect a success story, there is need to establish trust among police organizations and civil society. There is need to upgrade the old Public Relation with modern day PR. Regular community connect initiatives must be carried out in more organized manner by keeping a track record of all events, such strategic and organized attempts holds the pivotal key in making society crime free through effective public police interface.

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